

Some Polyoxyethylene Fatty Amine Surfactants

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Manuscript received 3 August 1995, revised 9 April 1996, accepted 16 July 1996

Many polyoxyethylene derivatives are surface active agents¹. Tanimoto *et al.*² showed that polyoxyethylene stearylamine selectively improves methane fermentation and inhibits sulphate reducing bacteria. The possible relationships between surface properties and biological activity have been increasingly investigated. Thus, Mathews³ showed that micellar aggregation is a necessary concomitant of the inhibiting action of a homologous series of fatty alkyl sulphates on hyaluronidase. The increase of critical micelle concentration and lowering of surface tension of sodium *N*-acyl sarcosinates⁴ and sodium dodecylbenzene sulphonate⁵ are associated with higher antimicrobial efficiencies of these compounds.

The aim of the present work was to contribute to this area of research. Thus, a series of polyoxyethylene fatty amines was prepared, tested for their fungicidal activity and some of their surface properties were determined. Besides, structure-activity relationships and the effect of surface properties on fungicidal activity were studied.

Results and Discussion

The polyoxyethylene fatty amines (1-4) were prepared

via the interaction of a fatty amine $C_xH_{2x+1}NH_2$ ($x = 10, 12, 16, 18$), 1,2-dichloroethane and the appropriate polyoxyethylene glycol (200, 400, 600 or 1000). Infrared spectra of the compounds showed bands at 3 400-3 430 (OH, probably overlapping NH), 2 840-2 850 (sym CH_2), 2 945-2 955 (asym CH_2) and 1 110-1 120 cm^{-1} (C-O).

1; R=C₁₀H₂₁, 2; R=C₁₂H₂₅, 3; R=C₁₆H₃₃, 4; R=C₁₈H₃₇
a; $n \approx 5.1$, b; $n \approx 9.7$, c; $n \approx 14.2$, d; $n \approx 23.3$

Surface properties showed that effectiveness (π_{CMC}), hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB), critical micelle concentration (CMC), surface activity ($-d\sigma/d \log c$) and area per molecule (A_{min}) of the compounds (Table 1) increased with the increase of the chain-length of the hydrophilic moiety and decreased with the increase of the chain-length of the hydrophobic moiety. It was observed that A_{min} increased with the increase of the chain-length of both hydrophilic and lipophilic moieties.

The compounds were screened for their antifungal activities^{6,7} against *Asperigillus flavus*, *A. niger*, *A.*

TABLE 1—SURFACE PROPERTIES OF POLYOXYETHYLENE FATTY AMINES (1-4) AT 30°

Compd. no	Oxyethylene unit	HLB	CMC mol dm ⁻³	$\frac{-d\sigma}{d \log c}$	$m \times 10^{10}$ mol cm ⁻²	$A_{min} \times 100$ nm	π_{CMC} dyn cm ⁻¹
	n						
1a	5.1	11.9	4×10^{-3}	5.2	1.43	11.6	32.5
1b	9.7	14.7	9×10^{-3}	6.1	1.38	12.0	36.5
1c	14.2	16.0	2×10^{-2}	6.5	1.37	12.1	38.5
1d	23.3	17.4	6×10^{-2}	6.8	1.25	13.3	42.5
2a	5.1	11.1	4×10^{-3}	5.3	1.40	11.9	34.5
2b	9.7	14.0	8×10^{-3}	5.9	1.36	12.2	36.5
2c	14.2	15.5	1×10^{-2}	6.8	1.32	12.6	39.5
2d	23.3	17.0	5×10^{-2}	6.9	1.25	13.3	42.5
3a	5.1	9.7	2×10^{-3}	4.7	1.32	12.6	32.5
3b	9.7	12.8	4×10^{-3}	5.4	1.25	13.3	35.5
3c	14.2	14.5	8×10^{-3}	5.7	1.21	13.7	37.5
3d	23.3	16.2	2×10^{-2}	6.1	1.10	15.1	39.5
4a	5.1	9.2	1×10^{-3}	4.3	1.30	12.8	30.5
4b	9.7	12.3	3×10^{-3}	5.2	1.25	13.3	34.5
4c	14.2	14.0	7×10^{-3}	5.6	1.18	14.1	35.5
4d	23.3	15.9	1×10^{-2}	5.8	1.13	14.7	37.5

ochraceous, *A. alternata*, *Cunninghamella echinulate*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Mucot racemosus*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Strachybotrys atra* and *Trichoderma viride* at concentrations 500, 1000 and 2000 mg ml⁻¹. All the compounds showed antifungal activity against all the fungi except *A. niger* on which the compounds showed no activity.

Experimental

Fatty amines and polyethylene glycols (both Aldrich) were used.

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on an ATI Mattson FTIR spectrometer (Genesis series).

Surface tension was measured using a Du Nouy tensiometer (Kruss 8451) using 0.1% solutions at 30°. CMC was determined applying the surface tension method at 30°.

The fungal strains were isolated from either Egyptian soils or Nile River.

Polyoxyethylene fatty amines (1-4): A mixture of polyethylene glycol (0.1 mol), a fatty amine (0.1 mol), 1,2-

dichloroethane (0.1 mol) and KOH (0.2 mol) was refluxed for 8 h and the water formed was continuously removed during the reaction. The mixture was then acidified with concentrated HCl to pH 3-4. The crude polyoxyethylene fatty amine was separated by salting out and purified by extraction with isopropanol (3 × 250 ml).

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